

Ayurveda's Role in Diabetes Management and Its Best Practices

Diabetes is an extremely widespread health problem that affects close to 442 million individuals all over the world.

It is a condition in which the levels of sugar in the blood increase to dangerously high levels. This frequently occurs as a result of insufficient insulin synthesis. There is now no foolproof treatment available for diabetes, despite the seriousness of the problem. As a result, treatment consists of both medicine and preventative measures.

This blog explains diabetes as well as [Ayurveda](#) methods that can be used to control it. Read it if you are interested in learning how to keep your blood sugar under control.

Ayurvedic Treatment for Hyperglycemia and Diabetes

According to [Ayurveda](#), there are twenty different types of diabetes. These shapes emerge as a result of the body's various doshas configuring themselves in a variety of different ways.

There are ten conditions that are associated with the kapha-dosha, four that are associated with the vata-dosha, and four that are associated with the pitta-dosha.

Madhumeh is another name for type 2 diabetes in Ayurvedic medicine. It's a portmanteau made up of these two words:

- Madhu: Sweet (ness)
- Urinary wastes, also known as meh

Let's have a look at some of the more frequent factors that Ayurveda identifies as contributing to diabetes.

According to Ayurveda, some of the potential causes of diabetes are:

People are frequently unaware of what causes diabetes in their bodies. According to [Ayurveda](#), there are a number of lifestyle variables that could contribute to it. Here are some common diabetes triggers.

- A lack of physical exercise
- Unhealthy patterns and poor quality of sleep.
- Consuming an excessive amount of yoghurt.
- The ingestion of some kinds of animal flesh soup (domestic or marine in most cases).
- Engaging in practises that bring on a kapha state.
- Hereditary.

According to several citations found in Ayurveda, diabetes can manifest itself in any of the following two ways:

1. Dhatukshaya is a kind of diabetes that affects young people. This condition arises as a consequence of the depletion of tissue (dhatu) in the body.

Maintaining healthy levels of ojas is essential to proper digestion as well as the health of the tissues. In addition to this, Ojas energises the body, which in turn serves as a check on the mental and physical health of the individual. Diabetes mellitus, also known as Ojo Meha, is the ailment that occurs when the essence of life is lost by urinary excretion (ojas meha).

2. The term "avarana" describes the obstructing of channels within the body. This obstruction is due to large quantities of kapha, which can be found in tissues such as muscle or fat. This can also result in diabetes that begins in middle age.

Typical manifestations of diabetes

One should keep an eye out for the following signs before getting yourself checked out for diabetes:

- Polyuria (excessive urination)
- the sweetness of the urination
- Polydipsia (excess thirst)
- Diarrhoea
- Headache
- Burning sensation
- General debility

- Indigestion
- Necrosis
- Carbuncles
- Lesions associated with inflammation
- Loss of muscle mass
- Excessive sleep
- Sluggishness

Diabetes can affect a variety of different dhatus (tissues).

The following are some of the ways in which diabetes can influence different tissues (dhatus):

- RASA/plasma: Causes elevated blood sugar levels
- Rakta (blood): Blood cells that are of low quality, characterised by their high viscosity and their fragility.
- Mamsa/muscles: Atrophy of the muscle tissue.
- Adipose tissue hypertrophy, often known as medhas or fat.

- Asthi (bone): De-mineralization of bone tissues and low bone density.
- Majja/nervous tissue: Brain tissue deterioration.
- Shukra and other reproductive tissues: decreased libido and increased risk of passing the condition on to subsequent generations.
- Atherosclerosis in the arteries and SIRA.
- Necrosis, ulcers, and carbuncles are all examples of cutaneous conditions that fall under the Tvak umbrella.
- Snayu, also known as the nerves: neuropathies.

Diabetes treatments based on Ayurveda: what can be done to lower blood sugar levels?

The question "how to control diabetes without medicine" is probably something that comes up for a lot of people who have diabetes.

Although it may come as a surprise to you, it's not completely out of the question. The following are some natural diabetes management strategies recommended by Ayurveda.

1. For Managing Juvenile Diabetes Mellitus

Insulin is absolutely necessary for the treatment of diabetes of the juvenile type. However, it is possible that it will not resolve all of the issues. It is possible that the individual will continue to feel weak and will

remain susceptible to illness. A combination of insulin and Ayurvedic therapy is likely to be effective in preventing such illnesses.

Two herbs, namely Bhumyamalaki and Guduchi, contribute to the success of this treatment. In addition to this, it is essential to consume foods that are high in astringency and bitterness.

When there is a depletion of dhatu (also known as tissue), consuming nourishing foods in smaller quantities is appropriate. In autoimmune disorders, Ama, which refers to the digestive fire in the stomach, will require priority attention.

2. For the Treatment and Management of Mature-Onset Diabetes Mellitus

It is essential to determine the stage of diagnosis in order to successfully treat this form of diabetes.

Depending on the stage, the following practices can be helpful:

- Restrictions imposed on one's diet
- Suggestions concerning one's diet that have been made by a physician or nutritionist
- Certain herbal and Ayurvedic preparations could be of assistance
- It's possible that regular practise of the following yoga asanas could be beneficial:

- Mountain stance. - a dog stance with the person facing downward. - Doing the child stance. - The Bridge Position - Plank posture. - The "Tree" stance - Corpse position.

In addition, the panchakarma therapy is something you should consider doing if you are in decent physical shape. In the event that an individual does not have adequate physical fitness, the basti treatment, also known as the enema treatment, will be recommended.

3. Nutrition, Physical Activity, and Rest

Diabetes can be caused by a lack of sleep, as well as improper nutrition and inactivity. The adoption of a healthy lifestyle is one of the most effective methods available for managing diabetes.

The objective should be to maintain a healthy sleep cycle, evaluate your food, and engage in regular physical activity like yoga and exercise.

It is essential to stick to a diet in order to bring down your blood sugar level if you have diabetes of any kind. The following is a list of foods that may be included in this diet:

- Vegetables that do not include starch.
- Fruits - oranges, melons, apples, bananas, grapes.
- Grains
- Foods that are high in protein.
- Low-fat or no-fat dairy.

4. The tablet form of Glymin Plus

There are various herbs used in ayurveda medicine to regulate blood sugar, such as.

- Nishamalaki (Curcuma longa & Emblica officinalis)
- Guduchi (Tinospora cordifolia)

The name "Meshashringi" (Gymnema sylvestre)

- Asana (Pterocarpus marsupium)
- Jamun (Syzygium cumini)
- Salacia in conjunction with Shilajit

Glymin Plus tablets, which include the potency of these herbs, are available at the Kerala Ayurveda Store. These tablets can assist in preserving healthy levels of glucose in the blood.

5. Triphala Tablet

Kerala Ayurveda Constipation and other digestive difficulties can be treated with triphala tablet, which is an ayurvedic medicine and a natural remedy. In addition to these benefits, however, using Triphala tablets can also assist maintain a healthy blood sugar level.

Wrapping up

It is absolutely necessary to lead a healthy lifestyle if you want to control your diabetes. In this blog post, we explored diabetes, its causes, and several management strategies that may be helpful.

It is hoped that this was of some assistance.